

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Research Article

Formulation And Evaluation of Herbal Hair Serum Using Eclipta Alba Extract and Rosmarinus Officinalis Essential Oil

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 31 May 2025

Keywords:

Hair, Herbal Hair Serum,
Herbal Hair Care, Bhringraj,
Rosemary Oil

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.15559523

ABSTRACT

Hair plays a vital role in a person's identity and looks, but it is extremely prone to hair loss, dandruff, and dryness-all of which have the ability to damage one's self-esteem and general health. This project outlines the information on anatomy and physiology of hair, most common hair problems, available hair care products and thereby explaining why herbal hair serums could be a safe, natural solution for it, which is followed by formulation and evaluation of herbal hair serum using natural ingredients for general purpose. Varying concentration of ingredients and excipients were used to formulate different batches. These were tested and evaluated for its physical appearance, pH, homogeneity test, viscosity, skin irritation, spread ability test and stability test, also phytochemical screening of herbal extract was performed to check the presence of active moieties. All the test result parameters were found to be in acceptable standard limits, indicating the safety as well as efficacy of the herbal hair serum. Overall, herbal hair serums stand out as a sustainable and holistic option for today's hair care needs, supporting both beauty and health.

INTRODUCTION

Human hair is considered as one of the symbols of beauty and is integrated with individual identity, contributing to one's overall appearance and self-esteem. Hair can be defined as- "improved epithelial structure formed as a result of keratinization of germinative cells". It is primarily composed of keratin- a protein that providing strength and flexibility to the hair. Embedded in

hair follicles, hair roots receive nutrients through a network of blood vessels, enabling growth. Sebaceous glands present in hair follicles-secrete oils, aiding in the maintenance of hair's condition, while melanocytes produce melanin, giving hair its color.[7] Hair is slightly complex structure made up of keratin protein. The structure of hair is divided majorly into 2 main parts: -

1. Hair root: -

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

This part is present below the layer of skin, hence not visible. It consists of different parts as follows:

- **Hair bulb:** It is present at the terminal end of the hair root. It is a bulb shaped structure.
- **Hair follicle:** It is made up various layers. It is a tube-shaped structure which surrounds the hair shaft present below the skin.
- **Papilla:** It is present in between the hair bulb. It functions to provide Nutrients and blood to the hair in growing phase.

2. Hair Shaft:

This is the part that is present above the layer of skin and which is visible. It is made up of keratin protein. Hair shaft is mainly divided into 3 parts as follows:

- **Cuticle:** It the outermost layer of the hair shaft and it consists of scales that overlap each other. It functions to protect the hair and the inner layers of the hair shaft from various environmental factors.
- **Cortex:** It is the middle part of the hair shaft, also it occupies the largest area of hair shaft. It also contains melanin (hair pigment) which imparts colour to the hair.
- **Medulla:** It is the innermost layer of the hair shaft. It forms a hollow tube-like structure. Medulla can be absent in fine hairs.

Hair Growth Cycle: -

Hair growth cycle consists of four phases i.e Anagen, Catagen, Telogen and Exogen.

A. Anagen (Growth phase): It is the first phase during which, cells of the bulb divide rapidly, resulting in new hair growth. 80-90% of hair

follicles are in the anagen phase at any given time. The anagen phase lasts for 2-7 years. The time upto which the hair remains in anagen phase is also determined by genetics.

B. Catagen (Transitional phase): The hair enters the catagen phase at the end of the anagen phase. This short, transitional phase lasts for only 2-3 weeks. During the catagen phase, the hair stops growing and detaches itself from the blood supply. The hair becomes club hair. In this phase the follicle renews itself.

C. Telogen (Resting phase): During this phase, the club hair rests while a new hair begins to grow beneath it. The new hair shaft develops once the telogen phase is complete. During this phase the follicle remains dormant for one to four months. The telogen phase lasts for 3 months. About 10-15% of all hair are in this phase at any one time.

D. Exogen (Shedding phase): The exogen is the last part of the hair cycle. During the exogen phase, the resting club hair detaches and falls out. Every hair eventually sheds, and it's completely normal to lose 50 to 100 hair each day. After the exogen phase, the follicle then returns to the anagen phase and the cycle repeats. [7, 31]

Various hair problems: [9, 13, 14, 25]

1. **Dandruff:** Dandruff is a common condition that causes the skin on the scalp to flake.

2. **Hairfall:** Hair loss is unusual shedding of high amount of hair, it can be temporary or long lasting.

3. **Oily /greasy hair:** Excessive sebum production, results in greasy, oily hairs.

4. Dryness and frizz: It is condition which occurs due to lack of moisture in the hair.

5. Split ends: Split ends occur when the hair cuticle gets damaged and starts to peel away, causing the hair to split into two or more strands.

6. Premature graying: It is a condition of graying of hairs, where the hair loses its pigment(melanin) and becomes gray or white in colour.

7. Hair thinning: In this condition there is a decrease in the volume of hair due to the thinning of the hair shaft.

Prevention of hair problems: [13, 14, 15]

1. **Manage Stress:** Stress affects overall health. It can even help trigger dandruff or worsen existing symptoms.
2. **Eat a Healthy Diet and Hydration:** A balanced diet that provides enough nutrition may help prevent dandruff and other hair issues. Drink water helps retain hydration.
3. **Often Shampooing:** If an individual has oily scalp, daily Shampooing may help to prevent dandruff.
4. **Get Enough Sunlight:** Morning sunlight is good for scalp and hair, but extreme heat and exposure to UV light may damage the hair.
5. **Limit Hair Styling Products:** Hair styling products can build up on the hair and scalp, making them oilier.
6. **Use Appropriate Hair Care Products:** Products suitable to your hair type and scalp should be used.

Various available hair care products: [17, 25, 26]

1. **Conditioner:** Conditioners help to moisturize the hair, and they come in different formulations, like protein conditioners for damaged hair and with ingredients like argan oil for hair smoothness and shine.
2. **Hair Oils:** It can nourish and protect the hair, and hair oils often include ingredients like coconut oil or onion oil for hair growth and strength.
3. **Hair Serums:** Hair Serums can help to reduce frizz. They add shine, and protect hair from damage, with specific hair types and related problems
4. **Hair Masks:** Hair masks provide intensive nourishment for hair damage and dryness and frizz. Contains ingredients like onion oil and coconut oil.
5. **Shampoo:** Shampoos are useful for cleansing the hair and provide smoothness and shine to hairs. Also reduces oils, frizz from scalp and reduce dandruff.

Introduction to Hair Serum:

Healthy hair is characterized as shiny, voluminous, and free from any kind damages. However, hair issues such as hair loss, dandruff, premature graying and baldness are commonly observed and are found to impacting individuals' self-esteem and quality of life. But as peoples want to remain young and attractive, lead to development and increased use of cosmetics. Herbal cosmetics are products that are made from a variety of permissible cosmetic ingredients to serve as the basis on which one or more herbal ingredients are used to achieve specified cosmetic benefits [3]. Hair serums, a category within cosmeceuticals,

provide a convenient solution to various hair problems, these have a high amount of active ingredient in their formulation for providing nourishment to hair and scalp, offering- frizz control, shine enhancement, and protection from environmental damages. It can also address specific hair concerns such as dryness, damage and growth promotion etc. [9, 10]

Rationales for our Herbal Hair Serum Formulation:

- **Natural Ingredients:** This serum is formulated using natural herbal extracts and oils, including Bhringraj, Amla, Hibiscus, Aloe vera, Rosemary oil and other varieties of natural elements.
- **Two-Phase System:** The procedure describes the preparation and combination of an “Aqueous Phase” and an “Oil Phase,” suggesting a well-emulsified or biphasic serum design for potentially better ingredient delivery and aesthetic feel.
- **Easy Application:** Serums are typically designed for topical application directly to the scalp, with a spray for targeted use.
- **Non-Greasy/Lightweight Formula:** Most are formulated to absorb quickly without leaving a sticky or greasy residue.
- **Suitable for Various Hair Types:** This serum was designed to be effective across different hair types, although some may target specific concerns like oily or dry scalps.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

I. Key Herbal Ingredients Used in Herbal Hair Serum: [4, 5, 6, 8, 12, 23, 27]

1) Bhringraj:

Botanical Name: Eclipta alba or Eclipta

Family: Asteracea

Composition: Wedelolactone, ecliptine, alkaloids, flavonoids, saponins, coumestans, polyacetylenes, phytosterols

Function: It's widely recognized for its ability to promote hair growth, reduce hair fall, prevent baldness, and treat conditions like dandruff and scalp infections. It's also believed to help maintain natural hair color.

Fig 2: Bhringraj

2) Rosemary Oil:

Botanical Name: Rosmarinus officinalis, Salvia Rosmarinus

Family: Lamiaceae

Composition: Carnosic acid, ursolic acid, camphor, cineole, rosmarinic acid, alpha-pinene etc.

Function: Often used for its ability to stimulate blood circulation in the scalp, which can promote hair growth and prevent hair loss. It also has antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties, and can help with dandruff and itchy scalp.

Fig 3: Rosemary Oil

3) Amla:

Botanical Name: Phyllanthus emblica, Indian gooseberry

Family: Phyllanthaceae

Composition: Vitamin C, gallic acid, ellagic acid, flavonoids, tannins, iron, calcium

Function: A rich source of vitamin C and antioxidants. It strengthens hair follicles, reduce hair breakage, prevent premature graying, and add shine to the hair. It's also believed to condition the scalp and promote healthy hair growth.

Fig 4: Amla

4) Hibiscus:

Botanical Name: Hibiscus rosa-sinensis, Indian hemp

Family: Malvaceae

Composition: Anthocyanins, phenolic acids, AHAs, amino acids, mucilage, flavonoids

Function: Known for its conditioning and softening properties. It helps to make hair smoother and more manageable, adds shine, and can promote hair growth. It's also used to prevent hair fall and premature graying.

Fig 5: Hibiscus

5) Aloe Vera:

Botanical Name: Aloe barbadensis miller

Family: Liliaceae

Composition: Polysaccharides, vitamins (A, C, E, B12), minerals (Ca, Mg), enzymes, amino acids

Function: A soothing and moisturizing ingredient. Its gel-like consistency helps to hydrate the scalp and hair, reduce dryness, and soothe irritation or inflammation. It also contains enzymes that can help to repair dead skin cells on the scalp, promoting healthier hair growth.

Fig 6: Aloe vera

II. Experimental Procedure:

Collection of plant:

The Bhringraj (*Eclipta alba*) leaves were collected from 'Senior Citizen Park' located in Kharghar sector 4, near Balbharti Public School in January 2025. While Aloevera (*Aloe barbadensis miller*) and Hibiscus (*Hibiscus rosa-sinensis*) are self-growned plants from students, and dried Amla (*Phyllanthus emblica*) was collected from Pharmacognosy department, B.K. Patil college, Taloja Phase 2, Navi-Mumbai.

Authentication of plant:

The Bhringraj leaves was verified and authenticated in research laboratory, in Botany department at Mithibai College of Arts, Chauhan Institute of Science & Amrutaben Jivanlal College of Commerce and Economics, Vile Parle(W), Mumbai.

Extraction method:

The collected plant samples of were thoroughly cleaned with water, Bhringraj leaves were left for drying for 2-3 days. Separately 100-150ml of water were used to soak 10 grams of each plant material- Bhringraj leaves, whole dried Amla and Hibiscus flower. This decoction process lasted for 4-6 hours at room temperature with intermittent

shaking. Later these were separately boiled on water bath for 15-20min at low flame. After cooling, the liquid extract was obtained by filtering with muslin cloth. In this way nearly 70-80ml of each Amla, Bhringraj and Hibiscus extracts were prepared and stored. [2, 7]

Fig 7: Bhringraj
Extraction

Procedure for Formulation of Herbal Hair Serum:

Step 1: All the ingredients were weighed and accurately measured.

Step 2: As per the above-described extraction procedure, separately extracted Bhringraj, Amla and Hibiscus- extracts nearly 80ml each collected in separate containers.

Step 3: Similarly, extract and collect the fresh aloe-vera gel in another container.

Step 4: Aqueous Phase - In a beaker take required quantities of Bhringraj, Amla, Hibiscus extracts followed by addition of fresh Aloe vera extract and Sodium benzoate with continuous stirring

Step 5: Oil Phase - In another beaker, take required quantities of Glycerine with Rosemary Essential Oil, it was followed with addition of Polysorbate 20 with continuous stirring for better emulsification.

Step 6: The Aqueous Phase was placed on magnetic stirrer, and the Oil Phase was then added to it with continuous stirring for at least 15-30min to ensure a homogenous solution.

Step 7: In Similar way as per the Formulation table 1, different test batches were prepared.

Step 8: All the batches were properly evaluated/tested and stored in a well closed container. [2, 5, 7]

Fig 8: Formulation of batches

Formulation Table:

Table 1: Ingredients List

Sr. No	Ingredients	Quantity (50ml)				Role of Ingredient
		Batch F1	Batch F2	Batch F3	Batch F4	
1.	Amla Extract	10ml	12ml	8ml	6ml	Strengthens roots, antioxidant
2.	Bhringraj Extract	10ml	12ml	8ml	10ml	Hair growth stimulator
3.	Hibiscus Extract	10ml	6ml	12ml	12ml	Conditioner, adds shine
4.	Aloe vera gel Extract	15ml	15ml	15ml	15ml	Base & moisturizer
6.	Rosemary Essential Oil	0.5ml	0.5ml	0.5ml	1ml	Scalp stimulant, Antimicrobial
7.	Glycerin	1.5ml	1.5ml	1.5ml	2ml	Humectant & Emulsifier
8.	Polysorbate 20	1ml	1ml	1ml	2ml	Emulsifier
9.	Sodium Benzoate	0.02gm	0.02gm	0.02gm	0.02gm	Preservative
10.	Triethanolamine	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Adjustment pH
11.	Distilled water	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	Q.S.	

III. Phytochemical Screening: [32]

For conducting the phytochemical screening, aqueous extracts prepared above was taken, and series of test were performed for screening of Alkaloids, Saponin, Carbohydrates, tannins and others and its result is mentioned in Table 3.

IV. Evaluation Parameters of Herbal Hair Serum: [1, 2, 9, 16]

1. Physical Appearance:

The visual inspection of the herbal hair serum involves evaluating its physical characteristics, color, odor and consistency.

2. Homogeneity Test:

An object glass that was clean and dry had hair serum smeared onto it, followed by sealing it with a cover glass. The presence of coarse particles or homogeneity was examined under light. Visual inspection was conducted on the herbal hair serum to check for homogeneity and to test for any lumps, flocculates, or aggregates.

3. pH Test:

The pH meter underwent calibration with pH 4 and pH 7 buffer solutions. Subsequently, the electrode was immersed in the hair serum and allowed to sit until the pH stabilized within a few minutes.

4. Viscosity:

The Brookfield viscometer (RVDV-II+PRO) was used to perform the viscosity measurement using spindle number 6. A beaker containing 50 ml of hair serum was utilized, and the viscosity was measured at different rpm values, specifically 10, 20, 50 and 100.

5. Skin Irritation Test:

After applying the serum to the skin, it is checked for any redness or itching after two hours.

6. Spreadability:

A similar plate procedure that is frequently used to evaluate and measure the spreadability of semisolid medicines was utilised to measure spreadability. One ml of hair serum was compressed between two 20 x 20 cm vertical plates, the upper of which weighed 125 g. After one minute, the spread periphery was measured. Spreadability was calculated using the following formula:

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Where, S = Spreadability

M = Weight in the visage (tied to the upper slide).

L = The glass slide changed the length.

T = Time (in sec) taken

7. Stability Test:

The herbal hair serum underwent storage for a duration of 7-days at two distinct temperatures of $4 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $30 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$, alongside 65% RH. Following this period, an assessment was conducted to compare the initial pH and viscosity values with those obtained after the 7-days storage period.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

I. Result of Phytochemical Screening: [32]

Table 2: Phytochemical Testing

Sr.no	Test Name	Chemical test	Observation	Result
1		Test For Alkaloids		

	Drangdorff's test	Nearly 1ml extract + Dragendorff's reagent	Orange brown precipitate indicates the Presence of alkaloids	Positive
	Wagner's Test	Nearly 1ml extract + Wagner's reagent.	Reddish brown precipitate	Positive
2	Test For Carbohydrates			
	Fehling's Test	The extract + Fehling's solution I and II and heated for few mins.	Red precipitate was obtained indicates presence of free reducing sugars	Positive
	Benedict's Test	Equal volume of the extract + Benedict's reagent	A red precipitate was formed	Positive
3	Test For Flavonoids			
	Alkali Test	Nearly 1ml extract + NaOH Solution (10%)	Yellow orange colour was produced indicating the presence of flavonoids	Positive
	Lead Acetate	To the test solution + few drops of lead acetate solution	It gives white precipitate.	Positive
	Test For Acid	To the test solution + few drops of conc. Sulphuric acid solution	Yellow orange colour was obtained	Positive
4	Test For Saponins			
	Froth Test	5ml extract + 5ml distilled water shaken for 30sec & left undisturbed for 10mins	Persistent froth indicated presence of saponins.	Positive
5	Test For Tannins			
	Ferric Chloride	1ml aqueous extract + 2ml 5% ferric chloride	Bluish black colour was produced indicates presence of tannins	Positive
6	Test For Protein and Amino Acids			
	Biuret Test	2ml extract + 1ml 10% NaOH solution & add few drops of copper sulphate and observe	Violet colour was obtained indicates presence of proteins	Positive
	Ninhydrin Test	1ml Extract + 1ml Ninhydrin solution, boil	yellow colour obtained absence of amino acid.	Negative

II. Result of Herbal Hair Serum Evaluation:

1. Physical appearance:

Under the physical appearance section; color, odor and texture of the formulated herbal hair serum are visually inspected and was found to be described in table 2:

Table 3: Physical Appearance

Parameter	Batch F1	Batch F2	Batch F3	Batch F4
Color	Pinkish-brown	Pinkish-brown	Pinkish-brown	Pinkish-brown
Odor	Rosemary oil scent	Rosemary oil scent	Rosemary oil scent	Rosemary oil scent
Texture	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth	Smooth

2. pH and Homogeneity Test

Table 4: pH and Homogeneity

Parameter	Batch F1	Batch F2	Batch F3	Batch F4
pH	5.54	5.40	5.42	5.6
Homogeneity	Good	Good	Good	Good

Fig 9: pH testing

3. **Viscosity Testing:** Brookfield viscometer was used to determine viscosity with spindle no 6 with various RPM, result obtained are as follow in Table 4:

Table 5: Viscosity Test Result

Viscosity: RPM	10 rpm	20 rpm	50rpm	100rpm
Batch 1 (CPS)	168cP	128cP	72cP	40cP
Batch 2 (CPS)	155cP	121cP	82cP	48cP
Batch 3 (CPS)	148cP	118cP	74cP	37cP
Batch 4 (CPS)	174cP	132cP	81cP	51cP

Fig 10: Viscosity Testing

4. Skin Irritation Test:

Hair Serum was applied to skin and was observed for over 24 hours. No Irritation, redness or itching was reported. Absence of any irritation and redness indicates it is safe for human skin and use.

5. Spreadability:

All the samples were having good Spreadability application and were easily applied and spread.

Batches were randomly assigned to evaluate for following Spreadability equation values:

$$S = M \times L / T$$

Table 6: Results Of Spreadability Test

For 1ml	For 2ml	For 3ml	For 5ml
Weight applied(M) =125gm	M= 125 gm	M= 125 gm	M= 125 gm
Diameter after spreading(L) =4.9cm	L= 5.4 cm	L= 6.1 cm	L= 6.8 cm
Time(T)=60 Sec	T= 60 Sec	T= 60 Sec	T= 60 Sec
$S = M \times L / T$	$S = M \times L / T$	$S = M \times L / T$	$S = M \times L / T$
$S = 125 \times 4.9 / 60$	$S = 125 \times 5.4 / 60$	$S = 125 \times 6.1 / 60$	$S = 125 \times 6.8 / 60$
S= 10.2	S=11.25	S=12.7	S=14.1

6. Stability Testing:

After 7 days the assessment was conducted to evaluate the initial and final pH and viscosity values. This test reveals the formulation was stable throughout study period.

Table 7: Result of Stability Testing

Sr. No	Parameter	Initial	Final
1	pH	5.41	5.56
2	Viscosity at 50 rpm	81cP	83cP

CONCLUSION

This research aimed to develop a natural, safe, and effective herbal hair serum using commonly available and traditionally valued herbs-Bhringraj, Amla, Hibiscus, Aloe Vera, and Rosemary oil, providing a safer alternative to harsh & synthetic hair products. Through extraction, blending, and evaluation of trial batches, it was found that the serum was found to be physically stable, pH-balanced, and rich in bioactive compounds that promote hair strength and growth. It showed a suitable consistency for leave-on application and was aesthetically acceptable. These results altogether validate the safety, stability, and

functional efficacy of the serum in creating a clean, nourished scalp environment. This formulation bridges traditional herbal wisdom with modern cosmetic science, making it a promising commercial product. Future works should focus on longer-term stability studies, IR & UV studies, clinical trials at various age groups, standardization for scale-up and market comparison with existing serums that may improve shelf life and consumer acceptability.

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HOW TO CITE: Girijesh Maurya*, Divya Sawant, Shruti Koli, Omkar Rajpure, Habibuddin Qazi, Formulation and Evaluation of Herbal Hair Serum Using Eclipta Alba Extract and Rosmarinus Officinalis Essential Oil, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2025, Vol 3, Issue 5, 5083-5095. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15559523>

